

Minutes of the 43rd Experimenters' Meeting
The Cosener's House, Abingdon, Thursday 25th June 2009

Present:

Dr David Hooper ^{3,4}	(DAH)	Secretary
Mr Dan Housley ⁵	(DJH)	
Mr Chris Lee ⁵	(CFL)	
Dr John Nash ²	(JN)	
Dr Emily Norton ⁵	(EGN)	
Dr Graham Parton ^{1,4}	(GAP)	
Dr Jeremy Price ²	(JP)	
Mr Hugo Ricketts ⁵	(HMAR)	
Prof Geraint Vaughan ⁵	(GV)	Chair

¹British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC)

²Met Office (MO)

³NERC MST Radar Facility

⁴Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL)

⁵University of Manchester

Other abbreviations used in this document:

ARSF	(NERC) Airborne Research and Survey Facility
BLWP	Boundary-Layer Wind-Profiler
csv	comma separated variable (file format)
DPW	Dave Wareing
FAAM	(NERC/MO) Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements
FGAM	Facility for Ground-based Atmospheric Measurement (formerly UFAM)
GPS	Global Positioning System
LD	Les Dean
MSE	Mesospheric Summer Echo
MST(R)(F)	Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NCAR	(US) National Center for Atmospheric Research
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
NOAA	(US) National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
PC	Personal Computer
SRG	(NERC's) Services Review Group
UPS	Uninterruptible Power Supply

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

The minutes of the previous meeting were accepted without correction.

2. Matters arising

40.4.1 DAH to improve the short time-scale MST radar diagnostic tools in time for the 41st Experimenters' meeting.

COMPLETED

The tools for automatically-plotting the latest radar-derived 30-minute-averaged wind-profile data and the laser ceilometer cloud base data were already in place at the time of the 42nd meeting. Since then, DAH has made some slight improvements. For example, the plots now show the previous 24 hours' worth of data relative to the time at which the plot was created and not to the time of the last available data. This makes it easier to spot instances when the data acquisition has stopped unexpectedly. DAH reported that he would probably continue to make small improvements to these tools but that, since the main functionality was already in place, this action should be considered as being completed. He further reported that he had recently established how to generate e-mails from software. This facility will allow, for example, monitoring programs to send warning messages if there is a break in data flow.

40.4.2 DAH to install more strategically-positioned web-cams at the radar site as an aid to the remote diagnosis of problems.

COMPLETED

DAH purchased three new cameras in late March 2009 and installed them at the radar site in early April. At present these new cameras are not directed at any particular pieces of equipment. However, they can be deployed to anywhere within the bungalow should the need arise.

ACTION ITEM 42.3.1 GAP and DAH to immediately remove minutes relating to meetings held within the last three years from public visibility.

COMPLETED

ACTION ITEM 42.3.2 GV and DAH to check with DPW, as soon as possible, whether or not the specified number of electrical sockets for the large shed will suffice.

COMPLETED

Dave Wareing (DPW) agreed that two additional 13 A sockets should be added. A more-detailed report on the electrification of the large shed is given in Section 3d.

ACTION ITEM 42.4.1 DAH to synchronise the LD40's internal clock at the start of the turbulence campaign on 23rd March 2009.

COMPLETED

This was done at 11:15 UT on 23rd March 2009. The internal clock was found to have been running 27 s behind the actual time.

ACTION ITEM 42.6.1 DAH to request NERC Estates, as soon as possible, to delay carrying out work on the concrete instrument compound until after the end of the March 2009 turbulence campaign and to avoid carrying out any work on site during the two weeks of the campaign.

COMPLETED

Further details of the Estates work are given in Section 3c.

ACTION ITEM 42.6.2 DAH to be available on site during the week of 23rd - 27th March 2009 so that he can supervise the appropriate installation of instruments.

COMPLETED

DAH was on site from first thing on Monday 23rd March until the afternoon of Thursday 26th March 2009.

ACTION ITEM 42.6.3 DAH to operate the MST radar between 23rd March and 3rd April 2009 using the same observation format as for the 2008 turbulence campaign, i.e. with interlaced 150 m and 300 m resolution observations.

COMPLETED

DAH reported that, in agreement with CFL and DJH, he had implemented a slightly different observation format to the one used for the 2008 campaign. Further details are given in Section 4f.

3. Facility Report

3a) Outcome of NERC Services Review Group 2009

The current cycle of MSTRF funding ends in March 2010. Consequently a renewal application was submitted to NERC in the first week of January 2009. This was evaluated by the members of the NERC Services Review Group (SRG), who issued a set of comments and questions for each Facility under review in the middle of February. The SRG met in the first week of March in order to reach their final conclusions. Their overall opinion of the MSTRF was favourable and they recommended a renewal of funding. They acknowledged the uniqueness of the radar, its suitability for studies of Natural Hazards, and the high level of support provided by DAH to user scientists. At the same time they felt that the number of users needed to be increased. The following scores (out of 5.0) were awarded: 4.5 for Need, 5.0 for Uniqueness, 4.0 for the Quality of Science, and 4.5 for the Quality of Training. The average score of 4.5 (down from 4.75 for the previous review period) is deemed to be good.

3b) MST Radar Renovation

Over the 20 year lifetime of the MST radar, the beam-steering electro-mechanical relay units have been repeatedly reconditioned rather than being replaced. They are now deemed to have reached the end of their useful working lives. This degradation is thought to be the primary reason for a reduction of almost 5 km in the maximum useful altitude for wind-profiling purposes over the past decade. Moreover, many of the control cables for these units have suffered from severe vermin damage and will also need to be replaced. Although the original beam-steering unit is still in good working order, its lack of documentation will make it difficult to repair in the case of a failure. Owing to the likely cost of replacing these components, the Facility is obliged to go through an EU competitive tender process in order to find a supplier. NERC has made money available for this purpose in connection with the renewal of recurrent funding. It is anticipated that the renovation work will take place in early 2010.

JN advised DAH to specify that the replacement components should be capable of being tested. Otherwise the causes of reduced performance can be difficult to identify. He reported that the South Uist radar is still not performing as well as it should be for reasons unknown. He drew attention to failures of the South Uist and Aberystwyth radars to detect important regions of strong winds (i.e. speeds of 80 - 90 m s⁻¹). He was not sure whether this was caused by a lack of signal strength or whether it represented a failure of the signal processing to track such high speeds.

ACTION ITEM 43.3.1 JN to inform DAH of the days on which the Aberystwyth MST radar failed to measure strong winds and DAH to investigate the cause of this failure.

3c) NERC Estates Work

A list of necessary estates work to be carried out at the MST Radar site was drawn up by a team from NERC who made an inspection in September 2007. It was finally put into action during the period 2nd - 20th March 2009. Work was carried out by a variety of sub-contractors under the co-ordination of the Aberystwyth University Estates team. The simultaneous presence of so many teams carrying out unrelated tasks around the site made for a great deal of disruption. However, the end result has been worth it. The most noticeable improvement is that the site has been stripped of all superfluous vegetation. The bungalow had literally begun to be over-grown by July 2008 (when, as an intermediate measure, a 2 m exclusion zone had to be cut around it). A robust-looking new main gate and replacement entrance signs now project an improve first impression to visitors to the site. A few jobs remain outstanding. For example, the trip switch for the along-track lighting circuit needs to be replaced. DAH discovered that it was causing the master switch to trip immediately prior to him arriving at the site bungalow during the mornings of the March 2009 turbulence campaign. This was presumably a result of the light-activation motion-sensor being triggered by him approaching the main gates. The circuit had to be isolated in order to prevent the radar from powering down unexpectedly during the course of the campaign. It has yet to be switched back on. All work was funded by NERC Services and Facilities and project-managed by NERC Estates.

3d) Electrification of the large shed

Despite the fact that NERC had made money available for this job at the beginning of the 2008-2009 financial year, it proved almost impossible to find a contractor who was willing to undertake such a "small" job. The work was finally carried out in the last week of February 2009. The shed now has a dedicated electricity supply and distribution board. DAH drew attention to the fact that the shelter provided by the shed had proved to be invaluable during the March 2009 turbulence campaign. The gustiness of the wind on some of the days had made even the launching of radiosondes problematic. Inflating the balloons outside of the shed would have been impossible.

In response to a picture of one of the radiosonde launches shown by DAH, JN commented that it is better to stand upwind of the balloon when launching a radiosonde. In this particular case, that would likely have caused the unwinder (which connects the radiosonde to the balloon) to have become snagged on the person releasing the balloon. JN suggested that the unwinder could be dispensed with under such circumstances and the radiosonde could be attached directly to the balloon. However, this is only appropriate for tropospheric profiling as the the accuracy of the temperature measurements in the stratosphere would be reduced.

3e) Changes to MSTRF technical support

Les Dean (LD), a technician from the Institute of Mathematics and Physics at Aberystwyth University, began visiting the site at the beginning of February 2009. This allowed him a 6 week period of overlap with Tony Olewicz, who retired from his role as MSTRF site manager at the end of March 2009. LD is providing 10 hours a week of technical support, typically visiting the site on Tuesday and Friday mornings. This arrangement has worked well so far. However, there will inevitably be times when equipment cannot be restored to working order as rapidly as was previously possible.

3f) MSTRF on the BBC

The BBC programme "Wind", for which GV had been filmed at the radar site in August 2008, was first broadcast on BBC4 on 27th April 2009. It was repeated on BBC2 on 13th May. DAH recommended the programme overall and complimented GV in particular for his contribution to the programme.

3g) University of Manchester Environmental Science student visit

Approximately 48 Environmental Science undergraduates from the University of Manchester visited the radar site, in two groups, on 16th and 17th April 2009. On each day the students were split into three subgroups and rotated through talks given by GV (about the FGAM equipment), by DAH (about the MST radar), and by DPW (about the lidar equipment). CFL demonstrated a single radiosonde launch on each of the two days.

3h) Electricity

There was a power failure in the Capel Dewi area between approximately 13:00 and 14:20 UT on 27th April 2009. DPW arrived on site, and informed DAH of the situation, shortly after the Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) units had become discharged. Consequently there was no opportunity to shut down equipment in a controlled manner. Nevertheless, all PCs apart from Gaius (which acquires Ceilometer data) came back up automatically when the power was resumed. Augustus (which controls the MST Radar) couldn't restart operations until 16:45 UT owing to the fact that it performs lengthy disk checks each time it is restarted.

4. NERC Instrument Report

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

There is a gap in the recorded data between 15th May and 8th June 2009. This was caused by a sporadic recurrence of a long-term problem with the "modem" unit, which connects the data logger (located in the field) to the acquisition PC (in the site bungalow). Previous problems with this unit had been attributed to a build-up of moisture inside the data logger box. Consequently, subsequent to drying out the unit inside the bungalow, LD enclosed it in a waterproof casing before re-attaching it to the sensors on 12th May. Nevertheless, communications with the unit could only be established sporadically and infrequently thereafter. On 5th June (a Friday), LD established that a poor internal electrical connection was likely to be the limiting factor - he "encouraged" a communications connection to be established by tapping the unit with a screwdriver. However, it was not immediately obvious that the logger had actually stopped acquiring data on 15th May. This was a result of LD power-cycling the instrument (which caused it to lose its acquisition program) in an attempt to diagnose the original problem. DAH spotted this on the following Monday (8th June) and re-installed the acquisition program. Finally, a new modem unit had to be ordered after the existing one stopped working again on 22nd June 2009. There was no loss of data associated with this final incident.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

There have been no problems with the data acquisition over the past 6 months.

DAH drew attention to the fact that BADC have recently defined an implementation of a comma-separated-variable (csv) file format, which they are proposing for use with one-dimensional datasets. The new format will be particularly important for the large number of BADC users for whom Excel is the primary data analysis tool. Excel cannot read the netCDF format, which is recommended by the BADC owing to its ability to adopt the powerful Climate and Forecast (CF) metadata conventions (metadata means information about the data). Although Excel can read NASA-Ames files, these have relatively-limited opportunities for the inclusion of metadata. The new BADC-csv format has been designed with the adoption of CF conventions specifically in mind.

DAH suggested that the new format could be used for the MSTRF's one-dimensional datasets. There was a strong consensus that netCDF files were not so easy to use and that the simpler BADC-csv format should be used where possible.

ACTION ITEM 43.4.1 GV to provide DAH, by the time of the 44th meeting, with sample computer code used by members of his (GV's) group to read MSTRF data from netCDF files. DAH to make the sample code available through the Facility's website as soon as possible.

4c) Vaisala WXT510 surface met and wind sensors

There have been no problems with this instrument over the past 6 months. However, a small problem with the software which generates the netCDF files from the data-log has led to a few one-day files being missing from the BADC. The software crashes when there has been a gap in the data acquisition, e.g. following by the electricity supply failure on 27th April 2009. DAH will be able to generate the missing files as soon as he has identified and fixed the bug. DAH also plans to adopt the plotting style currently used to show the latest 24 hours' worth of data for the day-by-day plots stored on the BADC.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

There have been no problems with this instrument over the past 6 months.

4e) Sky camera

There have been no problems with this instrument over the past 6 months.

DAH focused on images recorded between 17:00 and 19:00 UT on 25th March 2009, i.e. during the first week of the turbulence campaign. These show a clear example of Kelvin-Helmholtz billow patterns, which are associated with wind shear and turbulence, in a thin cloud layer. The ceilometer data show a cloud base at around 2 km for most of this day. JP speculated that the sky-camera images suggested a significantly higher cloud base. The sky-camera looks quasi-horizontally whereas as the ceilometer is directed towards the vertical. Consequently the two instruments could be observing different layers. DAH suggested that, nevertheless, the sky-camera images should not be overlooked as a potential source of non-quantitative turbulence information. Unfortunately the large wind speeds throughout most of the troposphere on this day prevented useful beam-broadening-corrected spectral width values from being available.

4f) MST Radar

The standard (300 m range resolution) ST-mode cycle sequence involves making a vertical beam observation at every other dwell. This has been found to be particularly well-optimised for wind-profiling purposes, since the vertical velocity can change significantly over time scales of just a few minutes. Horizontal wind components are derived by combining the radial velocities for each off-vertical beam with that of the vertical beam which is closest to it in time. However, during the March 2009 turbulence campaign, only a single vertical beam observation was made each cycle (they were still made at every other dwell for the additional 150 m range resolution dwells). Moreover, the total cycle time was raised from 4 minutes 48 s to 9 minutes 36 s. This meant that the 30-minute-averaged wind-profiles produced for the Met Office were derived from just 3 rather than 6 instances of single cycle data. DAH deliberately left the campaign mode running (from 23rd March) until 5th May to see whether this sub-optimal strategy lead to a degradation of the Met Office model-comparison statistics for April 2009. Surprisingly it does not appear to have done so.

When the standard cycle sequence was resumed on 5th May 2009, DAH switched from the use of a Rectangular to a Hanning weighting window in deriving the Doppler spectra. A Hanning window had previously only ever been used for the first two months of operation of the new radar control and data acquisition system, i.e. in February and March 2007. However, the immediately-apparent reduction in Met Office model-comparison statistics (which was caused by a range gating problem) was initially attributed to this change and the use of a Rectangular window was readopted. As expected, there has been no apparent change in the Met Office model-comparison statistics since use of a Hanning window was reintroduced.

The first unambiguous example of a Mesospheric Summer Echo (MSE) for the 2009 season was seen on 6th June. The timing is similar to that for the 2008 season (8th June) but is later than has been seen in previous years (29th May in 2007, 27th May in 2006, and 3rd June in 2005). Since the beginning of the 2009 season, MSEs have been seen on most days. There has even been an example of a "midnight echo" in the early hours of 18th June.

At the previous meeting it was reported that the radar had suffered from a new type of interference during periods of very cold weather. The problem disappeared shortly after the extractor fan - which causes outside air to be drawn into the transmitter room - was switched off. Subsequent instances of this type of interference were confined to 31st January and 1st February 2009. In April 2009, LD installed a thermostat unit which will automatically switch off the extractor fan when the temperature in the transmitter room drops below and pre-set threshold.

The more-typical type of interference, which is associated with high temperatures in the receiver room, continues to be seen sporadically. During the last 6 months there were 26 occasions for which the signal processing prevented it from contaminating the wind profile data: on 29th and 31st January, on 21st, 24th, 26th and 28th February, on 1st, 6th, 8th, 10th, 14th, 15th, 21st, 24th, and 28th March, and on 2nd, 3rd, and 5th April 2009. It is speculated that the cluster of cases in March was related to NERC Estates work being carried out on site. The contractors required access to the receiver room and so it was difficult to control its temperature. There have been 9 occasions during which some (typically mild) contamination of the wind profile data was apparent: on 31st January, on 20th, 22nd, and 24th February, and on 8th, 9th, 11th, 12th, and 21st June 2009.

The Met Office model-comparison statistics for the last 6 months do not suggest that there have been any significant problems with Aberystwyth data quality. JN commented that Aberporth radiosonde wind-profiles would provide a better reference against which to check Aberystwyth data quality. GAP drew attention to the fact that the BADC are now receiving high-resolution Aberporth radiosonde data with a delay of just one month.

5. Guest Instrument Report

5a) FGAM instruments

The boundary-layer wind-profiler (BLWP) has been in quasi-continuous operation at the MST radar site since February 2009. It was brought down to participate in the March 2009 turbulence campaign. Despite having needed a replacement T-R switch and UPS unit, it has enjoyed an unusually trouble-free deployment. The Elight lidar was also operated at the radar site in connection with the turbulence campaign.

5b) University of Manchester static instruments

The static ozone lidar was used for the first time since approximately 2000 in conjunction with the March 2009 turbulence campaign. The Leeds group will launch an ozonesonde from the site as part of the July 2009 phase of the campaign and intercomparisons will be made between lidar, aircraft and ozonesonde measurements. Ozonesondes require longer unwinders than regular radiosondes and so it will be important to restrict launches to calm days - c.f. Section 3d. DAH reminded HMAR that the BADC are still waiting for him to deposit CSIP ozone data with them.

ACTION ITEM 43.5.1 HMAR to deposit CSIP ozone data on the BADC before the 44th Experimenters' meeting.

The water vapour lidar was also operated during the March 2009 campaign. It can now be controlled

remotely from Manchester. It will be particularly important for DJH's work, which is aimed at gaining a better understanding of the fine-scale atmospheric refractive index structure. A FAAM overflight is planned in connection with this project for December 2009. It will require there to be a low and indefinite tropopause. The aircraft will fly in circular tracks at different heights above the MST radar whilst recording temperature data at 20 Hz. The performance of the FAAM's frost-point hygrometer needs to be validated. The aircraft has a turbulence probe in its nose but it may be possible to add an Ames probe on the wing so that intercomparisons can be made.

5c) Met Office GPS receiver

The Met Office (MO) are looking to reduce the interval between data (from the whole GPS network) being processed from 60 to 15 minutes.

JN explained the reason the MO's cloud radar had not worked when it was deployed to the MST radar site for the March 2009 turbulence campaign was that an internal cable had worked loose.

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) The March 2009 turbulence campaign - CFL

During the March 2009 phase of the turbulence campaign, the ARSF Dornier aircraft performed overflights of the MST radar site. It flew several parallel tracks in the cross-wind direction at a fixed number of altitudes (during the July 2009 phase, tracks will also be flown in the along-wind direction). The turbulence probe data were most useful for altitudes below 1500 m, with the vertical velocity variances being very small at higher altitudes. The spectra of perturbations in the individual wind components are quite spikey and so CFL applied smoothing prior to deriving a best-fit line. Gradients of close to $-5/3$ are typical. CFL speculated that a bump in the smaller wavenumber region of the spectra could represent a transition between gravity wave and turbulence activity. JP commented that a similar feature is seen in the spectra of Cardington turbulence probe data, which suggests that it represents a real phenomenon.

The biggest problem in interpreting the turbulence probe data is in deciding the largest scale size of motion which should be considered when making comparisons with the (MST and boundary-layer wind-profiler) radar data. The corresponding vertical velocity variance is highly sensitive to this value. The beam-broadening-corrected spectral widths for the MST radar show a background of slightly positive values. This is thought to represent a limitation of the radar technique since values of around zero were expected. CFL suggested that it would be useful to have access to near-real-time plots of unaveraged MST radar data for the July phase of the campaign.

ACTION ITEM 43.6.1 DAH to create a facility for automatically-plotting near-real-time unaveraged MST radar data in time for the July 2009 phase of the turbulence campaign.

6b) Case Studies of Rapidly Deepening Depressions - JN

The motivation for this study is to make recommendations of the observation requirements for the MO's future observation network. In particular it addresses the question of whether the information available from boundary-layer wind-profilers (BLWPs) is being exploited sufficiently. In one example of a rapidly-deepening depression, the frontal passage is seen very clearly by the Camborne BLWP. There is a region of strong wind shear and the melting layer can be seen at a lower altitude after the front has passed over. The signal-to-noise ratio gives a qualitative measure of humidity and so could reveal the region of descending dry air behind a front. For this particular day, wind profiles at 30-minute intervals were too coarsely spaced to resolve the relevant atmospheric details. Similar cases have been seen by the South Uist MST radar and the Isle of Man BLWP.

The MO's plans to install a network of instruments around London, which are capable of resolving at-

ospheric features of smaller than 100 km, will go ahead. JN needs to identify a number of new BLWP sites, although not all of these will necessarily be used. Wind-profilers are now seen as one of the more useful instruments to have. It remains to be determined which additional instruments will provide the best complementary data. The weather radar network is being upgraded at the same time and all instruments will be given Doppler capability. The MO has invested heavily in running their model at 1.4 km horizontal resolution as part of the same action.

6c) Report from MST12 - DAH

The Twelfth International Workshop on Technical and Scientific Aspects of MST Radar (MST12) was held in Canada during May 2009. DAH gave lectures on “Radar Scattering Mechanisms” and “Data Storage Standards For the Atmospheric Sciences” at the Radar School, which was held immediately prior to the main workshop. He drew attention to the following topics from the main workshop which he thought would be of interest to NERC MST Radar data users.

Allen White (from NOAA) gave a presentation on “atmospheric rivers”. These are relatively narrow flows of air which account for a disproportionately high percentage of moisture transport. They can be responsible for intense precipitation and flooding, for example, when they encounter the mountains of southern California. These features have similarities with those seen in the UK GPS-network humidity maps which JN has identified as later giving rise to localised storms. Michael Nicolls gave a presentation on inertia-gravity waves seen in the D region with the Poker Flat Incoherent Scatter Radar. He used ray tracing techniques to infer the location of the source of the waves.

There have been interesting improvements in radar hardware. NCAR have developed a modular and scalable 449 MHz wind-profiler system which is designed with portability in mind. It's not clear whether a radar operating in this frequency band could be used in the UK. The Leibniz group are building a new MST radar at Andenes. It will have an individual low-power transceiver attached to each antenna. This obviates the need for beam-steering electro-mechanical relay units, which are inherently prone to failure. This design caught DAH's attention in the context of the needs of the Aberystwyth radar - see Section 3b. However, although this would be a desirable solution if building a radar from scratch, it is unlikely to be achievable within the budget available for the Aberystwyth radar.

7. Any Other Business

The next meeting is provisionally scheduled for Thursday 21st January 2010 at the Cosener's House.